

“We have to learn to work with such systems”: Students’ Perceptions of ChatGPT After a Short Educational Intervention on NLP

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ABSTRACT

Natural Language Processing (NLP) is a critical area of AI that is increasingly integrated into everyday life. The public regularly engages with systems such as Siri, Alexa, and more recently, ChatGPT, yet few understand how these systems work. In this paper, we examine how students perceive NLP technologies after completing a unit on NLP within an AI course designed for non-CS majors. We further present our students’ perspectives on the banning of ChatGPT in Italy, where the course was delivered. The NLP unit featured a lecture, an interactive session, and a practical assignment wherein students developed a smart assistant responsive to textual commands. Students, after creating their smart assistants, highlighted challenges such as inadequate training datasets and natural language ambiguity. Opinions on ChatGPT’s ban varied, with privacy concerns prevailing. However, a consensus emerged in favor of educational efforts to raise awareness about technology limitations, advocating understanding over outright bans in anticipation of their inevitable integration into daily life.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Social and professional topics** → **Computing education**; • **Computing methodologies** → **Natural language processing**.

KEYWORDS

Artificial Intelligence, Natural language processing, Large Language Models, ChatGPT

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1 INTRODUCTION

Although NLP has been an active area of Artificial Intelligence (AI) research and development for decades, it has recently taken center stage in public discussions due to the rise of very “human-like” NLP

applications, powered by Large Language Models (LLMs) such as OpenAI’s generative pre-trained transformer (GPT) or Google’s LaMDA. Although LLMs have been in use for several years now, they have mainly operated behind-the-scenes in applications such as Web search auto-complete or machine translation. However, during the past year, much has changed, with the public having been introduced to *interactive applications* of LLMs, which have a variety of capabilities, such as generating coherent text (e.g., ChatGPT¹, BARD²), or computer code (e.g., CodePal³, CoPilot.⁴)

Applications of LLMs have proven extremely popular with users. In fact, OpenAI’s ChatGPT, released in November 2022, has become the “fastest growing consumer app” in the history of Web applications.⁵ However, there are many ongoing debates about LLM systems like ChatGPT, their benefits, and possible risks. One primary concern is that of biases within these systems. ChatGPT is trained on huge volumes of data from the Web, which reflect human biases [1]. These biases can be passed on to the model [28]. Studies have shown the existence of political biases in ChatGPT [29, 30]. Additionally, the issue of misinformation amplification arises as these models can inadvertently generate content that seems real but is actually made up with false or misleading information [5]. There have also been concerns from educators that students will use ChatGPT and other applications to cheat on their assignments, posing the risk that they will become overly reliant on them [34].

Recent research has considered integrating NLP technologies, particularly those based on LLMs such as ChatGPT, in education [8, 41]. Others have investigated how they perform on coding or providing feedback to students [2]. However, there is a lack of work that explores how educational interventions affect students’ perceptions of NLP and LLMs. It is important to understand whether students’ understanding and perceptions can change after attending related courses, which are designed to raise their awareness of these technologies. Our work begins to fill this gap.

Further to the educational challenges, privacy and ethical concerns are being intensely discussed by the research community [33], and organizations and governments have taken measures to mitigate the risks. Arguably, the most extreme position to date was that of the government of Italy, coincidentally, during the timeframe in which our course was offered. Specifically, on the 31st of March

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¹<https://openai.com/chatgpt>

²<https://bard.google.com/>

³<https://codepal.ai/>

⁴<https://github.com/features/copilot>

⁵<https://www.forbes.com/sites/cindygordon/2023/02/02/chatgpt-is-the-fastest-growing-ap-in-the-history-of-web-applications/>

2023, Garante, Italy’s data protection authority, banned ChatGPT in Italy due to concerns surrounding the privacy of personal data. After nearly a month of discussion and improvements, implementing changes to comply with several data privacy conditions, on the 28th of April 2023, ChatGPT was live again in Italy.⁶

Our contribution. Noting the gap in the literature concerning students’ understanding and perception of NLP and LLMs, as well as the current controversy surrounding ChatGPT in Italy, we investigated the impact of an educational intervention within our course. In this experience report, we present our experience of teaching students from various disciplines a unit on NLP as a part of an introductory course on AI. We used our students’ responses in one of the assignments to better understand how they perceive NLP technologies and capture their views on ChatGPT. Students’ responses revealed an appreciation for the challenges inherent in NLP systems, particularly in understanding ambiguity and the lack of relevant training data. Many students reported using ChatGPT for text composition or code generation. Regarding the ban on ChatGPT in Italy, privacy concerns were cited, underlining the necessity for regulations. Despite these concerns, they highlighted the need to embrace such technologies since they will inevitably be a part of our lives. Finally, a consensus emerged that rather than banning such tools, efforts are needed to educate the public on their use.

2 BACKGROUND

A growing number of studies consider the design of AI courses for different audiences, e.g., Computer Science (CS) students [12], K-12 students [19, 31] or the general public [13]. Several initiatives have included NLP in their curriculum, recognizing the need for learners to be educated in this field of AI as well [13, 31].

Studies have shown that most of the courses developed are for undergraduate and graduate CS students [23]. However, recently there has been an increasing number of AI courses designed for elementary school students [15, 20] and university students with diverse backgrounds [16]. A study of first-year non-CS students designed a curriculum for AI and Machine learning (ML) which covered the core concepts, implementation details, limitations, and ethical considerations of these topics [6]. Their findings show that non-CS students can comprehend AI and ML concepts without being overwhelmed [6]. A more recent study evaluated an AI course for university students with diverse backgrounds, has revealed improvement in students’ understanding of AI concepts, AI literacy, and ethical awareness [17]. Similarly, courses and training on ML in high school showed that students could understand and apply basic ML concepts, algorithms, and tasks [22].

On the other hand, with the recent hype surrounding the capabilities of LLMs and in particular, ChatGPT, there is increased research interest in the use of these technologies in education and their learning abilities [25]. Integrating them into classes promises to improve the individualization of education approaches, thus, some researchers argue strongly in favor of using them [4]. Studies explored the potential of NLP, particularly GPT-3, for personalized teaching and conversational interactions with students, revealing capabilities in accurately extracting equations and emulating

teacher-like communication, while recognizing limitations in effective student assistance [36, 41]. Assessments of ChatGPT’s coding capabilities showcased its proficiency in generating readable Java code [24] but revealed challenges in solving problems using object-oriented programming [3], and limitations in providing suitable feedback on programming assignments [2]. Additionally, evaluations of ChatGPT’s performance in educational tests underscored concerns about the potential misuse of these tools, as both studies demonstrated the tool’s efficacy in helping students cheat and achieve passing scores on assignments and exams [21, 34].

Other studies have focused on exploring the perceptions of different audiences regarding the use of generative AI, such as ChatGPT, in education. Generative AI tools like ChatGPT are inevitably being incorporated into courses and school assignments [27]. Research has shown that students are already using ChatGPT for academic purposes, including generating text and code, and they consider it a valuable tool [9, 40]. Conversely, a survey of instructors from 20 different countries revealed that while they are not currently using generative AI tools in their classes, they express a desire to do so in the future [26]. However, the use of ChatGPT in programming education has raised concerns; it can cause students to become lazy, provide incomplete or incorrect answers, and generate professional anxiety among students [39]. Therefore, there is a clear need for specific guidelines, more classroom assessments, and mandatory reporting of ChatGPT use [27]. Implementing certain restrictions on the use of generative AI tools in education and coursework is necessary to benefit both educators and students [26].

It is evident that there is a need for AI education emphasizing the demand for relevant and age-appropriate resources [10, 23, 32]. Studies highlighted the need for teaching AI to non-CS students [13]. We also noticed the gap in educational interventions for NLP and LLM education. In this paper, we describe our attempt to include a unit on NLP and LLMs in an introductory AI course which was designed for students with no CS background. We investigate our students’ understanding of NLP and their perceptions on NLP technologies such as ChatGPT after our educational intervention.

3 INSTRUCTIONAL UNIT

During the academic year 2022-2023, an introductory course on AI [11] was offered as an elective to non-CS students from the School of Innovation of the University of Trento, a public university in Italy. The course followed a blended learning approach, combining asynchronous (i.e., pre-recorded) lectures and synchronous interactive sessions. The course aimed to help students come to appreciate the nature of today’s AI, as well as to understand the basic elements of AI technologies, and how they are developed. Students became familiar with the fundamental definitions of and concepts around AI, but also, with the widespread methods used in the creation of systems. In particular, an introduction to data-driven AI, based on machine learning, was included as the second unit of the course. AI technologies such as Computer Vision, Natural Language Processing, and Personalization were also introduced. Finally, social and ethical issues of such technologies were also discussed.

One of the units focused on NLP. The unit aimed to ensure that students, can recognise NLP applications in their daily lives. Furthermore, the unit intended to enable students to recognize

⁶<https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-65431914>

potential risks associated with NLP, cultivating a critical perspective. It sought to develop students' ability to identify the challenges inherent in NLP. The unit comprised a pre-recorded video lecture lasting 21 minutes, which students were required to watch prior to attending a live session lasting one hour. Finally, they had to submit an assignment upon the completion of the unit and before the completion of the course.

In the video-lecture, the definition of NLP provided by IBM⁷ was presented. Next, key NLP tasks, e.g., speech-to-text, speech recognition, and machine translation, and applications relying on these tasks were discussed. To understand how NLP systems generally work, the typical NLP Cycle was presented, detailing how NLP systems are trained using ML, so it "understands" and/or generates natural (i.e., human) language. Students were then presented with examples of how NLP is used in tasks such as hate speech detection, sentiment analysis, and topic modelling. Finally, the benefits, challenges and possible drawbacks of NLP, were presented.

The live session commenced with a brief 10-minute recap of the unit, followed by a question and answer session (Q&A) and an interactive activity. The recap began by providing an explanation of what NLP is, followed by the presentation of the typical NLP Cycle. Social biases in NLP were also discussed (e.g., a sentiment analysis algorithm that systematically associates age-related words with negativity, a machine translation system that associates words (e.g., "doctor") with a particular gender when translated from English to a language with grammatical gender). During the live session, an interactive activity engaged the students in reflecting on their experiences with NLP. They were prompted to answer the question, "What are some things you like - and that you do not like - about an NLP application that you use?" Students were asked to contribute responses to a table on a shared document in which they wrote down the NLP systems they use as well as the positive and negative aspects of these systems. After the activity, the discussion shifted towards OpenAI's ChatGPT. The students explored the features and implications associated with this platform. Finally, the concept of Large Language Models (LLMs) was introduced, and students were presented with the challenges these technologies can bring.

4 ASSIGNMENT

The assignment aimed to help students understand the development and training process of smart assistants, which execute a task on the verbal command of the user. The assignment involved creating a smart assistant and then answering related questions. Students were provided with a step-by-step guide for creating a smart assistant for a smart classroom. In particular, the assistant would execute a set of tasks in the virtual classroom (e.g., opening or closing the lights). The guide was adopted from the ML for Kids platform⁸ [18]. Students used Scratch⁹ and the ML for Kids platform to create their assistant. During the live session, one of the instructors demonstrated how to use Scratch. Students were expected to have familiarity with the ML for Kids platform, as it was utilized in a previous assignment designed to facilitate their

learning of how to train ML models. Completing the assignment was estimated to require 1-2 hours.

Initially, students interacted with a working template of the smart assistant on Scratch, which utilized a rules-based approach and could only understand four predetermined commands (Figure 1a). Subsequently, students were instructed to develop and train their own machine learning (ML) model using the Machine Learning for Kids platform. They labelled each command and provided multiple examples to train the model, enabling it to recognize a broader range of commands (see Figure 1b).

Once their models were trained, students integrated them into their projects on Scratch. This integration expanded the assistant's ability to interpret and respond to a wider set of commands. The assistant leveraged patterns and examples to understand instructions. The final step of the smart assistant creation was to ensure the reliability and accuracy of the assistant; thus, students implemented a confidence score threshold of 70%. This threshold served as a measure of the assistant's confidence in understanding user commands correctly. Actions were performed only when the ML model's confidence score exceeded the predetermined threshold.

The assignment offered students hands-on experience in developing an AI-powered smart assistant while also fostering critical thinking about the complexities and ethical considerations inherent in AI/NLP systems. Once they completed their smart assistant, students answered questions related to the limitations of smart assistants and the challenges faced by developers when creating them. Furthermore, given the fact that during the course ChatGPT was banned in Italy, students were also asked to share their opinions on the ban. Students answered the following questions:

- Q1. Why do you think a smart assistant, such as Alexa or Siri, often does not understand what we ask it to do?
- Q2. What are the most difficult barriers that developers face?
- Q3. Have you ever used ChatGPT? If yes, how? If not, why?
- Q4. What is your opinion on banning ChatGPT in Italy?

Students. Although 29 students were registered to the course, 25 completed the assignment of the NLP unit. The majority was male (64%) and between 20-24 years old (64%), 24% of the students were between 25-29 and the rest were over 30. Most of the students were from the Economics and Management department (20%), followed by the Computer Science department (16%). Some others came from the Sociology and Social Research (12%), Psychology and Cognitive Science (12%), and Law (12%) departments. The rest of the students were from International Studies (8%), Civil, Environmental and Mechanical Engineering (8%), Cellular, Computational and Integrative Biology (8%), and Industrial Engineering (4%).

Analysis. We analyzed students' answers to Q1, Q2, and Q3, using open-coding, which is often utilized as a first approach in thematic analysis to identify interesting concepts [14]. Two researchers analyzed responses together, identifying the interesting concepts. Students' responses to Q4 were coded and thematically analyzed [38]. Two researchers analyzed the free-text responses independently to identify emerging categories. The identified themes were then compared, and the disagreements were discussed, to come to a final consensus. Multiple categories per answer were allowed.

⁷<https://www.ibm.com/topics/natural-language-processing>

⁸<https://machinelearningforkids.co.uk/>

⁹<https://scratch.machinelearningforkids.co.uk/>

Figure 1: (a) “Smart Classroom” on Scratch, and (b) Training dataset used to train the ML model for recognizing instructions.

5 FINDINGS

5.1 Challenges for smart assistants (Q1)

When students were asked to explain why they think smart assistants have difficulties in understanding humans’ instructions, six different reasons were provided. The most commonly discussed reason was the **lack of training examples** (19 out of 25). Students noted that assistants cannot understand because “*the model is trained with data that may not include all the possible scenarios*” (student 15 – s15). Others noted that “*the system has been poorly trained about a certain topic*” (s4) or that “*they are not trained for that specific phrase or meaning*” (s7). It was also noteworthy that some acknowledged that languages spoken less frequently may be less “understood” by smart assistants because the NLP algorithms do not have enough training data to learn them (s13, s17).

The second most common reason was the **ambiguity** of natural language (18 out of 25), with responses discussing different forms of ambiguity. Some students noted that “*Different interpretations or multiple meanings can lead to misunderstandings*” (s22). Others also pointed out that it is difficult to understand the person speaking because of their dialect (s1, s10, s11, s22), different accents (s11, s13, s22), or intonations (s5). One student mentioned that slang and “*implied meanings, hidden meanings and subtleties*” (s10) can also make it difficult for such systems to understand human commands.

Students often noted that one of the reasons smart assistants cannot understand is the **quality of the data** (8 out of 25). They explained that “[a]lthough algorithms behind smart assistants are trained with tons of information, they don’t always recognize the task that they are asked to perform” (s25) because “[they] may lack the necessary training data or specific instructions to handle certain types of queries” (s24). More specifically, one student noted that “*if the data used for training is insufficient or contains biases, it can impact their understanding and responsiveness*” (s22).

Students sometimes referred to the **technical difficulties** (6 out of 25) such background noises (s11, s13) or the audio quality (s3, s19) that can make it difficult for assistants to understand humans’ commands. Some also mentioned general technical issues such as lack of updates, lost connectivity (s23), or the system crashing (s18).

The two remaining reasons discussed by the students received few responses. The **confidence in the prediction** appeared only in five responses, some of the responses cited “*after developing a smart assistant, I have learned that when these AI tools tell us they*

don’t understand (or similar expressions) it could be linked to a lack of confidence in the answer” (s9). The least discussed reason was **difficulty in understanding human instructions** appearing only in four responses. These responses mainly noted that sometimes the instructions given by humans may be unclear (s2), or not concise (s10) and this can lead to misunderstandings.

5.2 Barriers when developing NLP systems (Q2)

When asked to ponder the most difficult barriers developers of smart assistants face, students mentioned ten different barriers. The most often discussed barrier was **ambiguity and complexity of the language**, appearing in 20 responses. These responses made reference to specific challenges such as understanding the different dialects (s22), different accents (s24) that exist, and different people speaking (s1). A large portion of the responses also mentioned that “*it is still difficult [...] to correctly understand the multiple senses, the ambiguity of a text and the different ways of expression*” (s21). A few students also noted the fact that humans often “*use of sarcasm and irony which is very tricky for programs to understand*” (s10).

Twelve responses referred to the difficulty of finding a **suitable dataset** to train smart assistants. While many responses indicated that it is hard to “*provid[e] specific and understandable examples; [and] being able to cover all possible [...] ways in which a request can be formulated*” (s2) a few responses noted that inconsistent or biased data can result in an inaccurate algorithm (s5, s25).

Two barriers received eight responses, tying for the second most common barrier: **difficulty in understanding human instructions** and **lack of training**. Differently from the responses discussing ambiguity and complexity of the language responses, these responses noted that “[u]nderstanding natural language commands and queries accurately is a complex task” (s22) further elaborating that “*human language often relies on implicit context and references to prior conversations or shared knowledge*” (s24). When discussing the lack of training, students mainly referred to “*the need for big data to train these models*” (s7) explaining that “*the more training data available, the better the classification will become*” (s15).

Five students mentioned **accuracy**, pointing out that “*converting spoken words into text accurately is crucial for understanding user commands*” (s24) and developers should “*ensure that these systems can perform the desired tasks accurately and as instructed*” (s18).

Four students mentioned **privacy** and **ethical considerations** as one of the biggest challenges. As one student highlighted "smart assistants frequently have access to private user information including location and contact details. Developers are responsible for making sure this data is secure and protected" (s3). They also noted that "[e]nsuring that systems are designed and deployed in an ethical manner can be a significant challenge and requires careful consideration of issues such as fairness, transparency, and privacy" (s5).

A few responses noted that developers must ensure that **processing and response times** are minimized (3 out of 25). Others mentioned that "a big challenge is creating a meaningful dialogue experience with its users" (s10) and making these systems **user-friendly** (3 out of 25). One student acknowledged the fact that it is a challenge "to include languages that are spoken by minorities" (s13) and another student referred to overcoming technical difficulties such as "background noise, or low-quality audio input" (s24).

5.3 ChatGPT (Q3–Q4)

The vast majority of the students stated that they have used ChatGPT (23 out of 25) and that "[i]t can be helpful for a variety of things, like inspiring creative writing, offering answers, and assisting with numerous applications" (s3). Most of them have used ChatGPT for doing some **academic work** (21 out of 25) such as text composition, studying, and programming. Nine students noted that they have used ChatGPT for **text composition**, for example, "for more fluently and cogently rewriting an email written in English" (s4), or "compose poetry, tell a joke, writing texts that connect very different topics, etc." (s13) or even to "invent poetry, songs, and blog posts" (s17). Other students indicated that they have used it to help them with their **studying** (7 out of 25) saying that they seek "explanation concerning a certain topic, that a professor would hardly explain in such a clear way" (s4). A few also mentioned that ChatGPT helps them with their **programming** (5 out of 25) "improving [their] code" (s5). Two students also mentioned that they are using it for **work purposes** and one student for getting **medical advice**.

Some students elaborated on why they are using ChatGPT noting that it is **efficient** (5 out of 25). Students explained that "[i]t simplifies research tasks and provides quick responses to specific issues" (s43) "allow[ing] [users] to save time" (s15). Some others mentioned that they used just for **fun** (4 out of 25), "to test how the system answers the questions and how "intelligent" ChatGPT really is" (s1). Some remarked that they were **impressed by the capabilities** (3 out of 25) of ChatGPT adding that "the NLP capabilities of ChatGPT have impressed me, and I appreciate its ability to generate human-like text" (s23). Three students reported that they were using ChatGPT **instead of a search engine** stating that "[they] use it as a substitute for Google, in fact with Google it is difficult and time-consuming [...], whereas by asking ChatGPT, [they] can immediately know the answer" (s6). Interestingly, two students noted that "[we] need to be a little careful **not to rely too much on the system**" (s1).

When it comes to students' opinions on banning ChatGPT in Italy, six stated that they **agree**, seven that they **disagree**, while the rest were **usure**. In their explanations about banning ChatGPT in Italy, seven themes emerged (see Table 1). It comes as no surprise that the most common theme was **privacy**. Responses noted that the reason for banning ChatGPT in Italy was because of concerns

about "privacy issues (basically, non-compliance with certain GDPR requirements)" (s13). Some also mentioned concerns about the collected data and how it is used (s10, s17) highlighting that "everybody should be informed about how its data is collected and processed, and for what purpose" (s25). Interestingly some students also referred to concerns about "misinformation, harmful content" (s22), "potential misuse, or ethical considerations" (s23).

Ten responses emphasized the need for **regulation** for AI systems like ChatGPT. The main idea shared by most responses was that governments (s22), "regulators, policymakers, and society" (s23) need to "regulate AI systems to ensure responsible use, protect user rights, and prevent misuse or abuse" (s22) "granting an AI that is lawful, ethical and robust with peculiar attention to fairness and explicability" (s9). Some students also pointed out that decisions for regulating or banning ChatGPT should be made by the EU (s5, s20) and "clear regulations would be needed, probably coming from the EU, to be in line with the GDPR" (s2). Some students also mentioned that the ban on ChatGPT was **limiting opportunities** (9 out of 25) of Italian residents. They noted that banning ChatGPT will "hurdle the Italian citizens' opportunity to keep up with this technology" (s21) or "utilize and benefit from such technologies" (s22).

Seven responses pointed the feeling of **fear** indicating that the decision for banning ChatGPT was "guided by the fear of a technology that is poorly understood" (s17) and "concern about how people might use ChatGPT" (s2). One student mentioned that "politicians are scared of innovation and uncontrollable situations" (s7) and that is why they made that decision. Some students noted that "If you are frightened of something, avoiding it is not a real solution" (s8).

The remaining themes received only a few responses. The **useful tool** (6 out of 25) noted that "ChatGPT and similar AI systems have the potential to assist in various tasks, improve productivity and provide valuable information" (s23). Responses also mentioned that we need to **embrace** (4 out of 25) such technologies noting that "ChatGPT and other LLM turned out to be game changers in the industry" (s11) and "[we should] not to be afraid of them, but work with them in a meaningful way" (s1) "since [they] will become even more necessary for the future" (s2). The least common theme, **education** (3 out of 25), highlighted that the "solution is not banning it but increase the concern and education around these tools" (s5).

We noticed that one response was generated by ChatGPT itself. It mentioned that "[critics] believe that AI models like me should not be restricted, as it limits people's ability to engage in open dialogue and express their thoughts and ideas freely" (s24). Interestingly, the response continues, noting that "Chat GPT models serve as valuable tools for educational purposes, allowing students, researchers, and developers to study and experiment with natural language processing, conversational AI, and related fields. Banning them could hinder educational and research progress in these areas" (s24).

6 DISCUSSION

In the context of an AI course for non-CS majors, delivered at a public university in Italy, we explored how students understand and perceive NLP technologies. With ChatGPT being banned in Italy for the duration of our course, it provided us with the opportunity to examine students' views and ideas for alternative approaches to protect citizens from the possible consequences of NLP.

Table 1: Themes emerged from Q4: name, description, and frequency.

Category	Description	#
Privacy	<i>Privacy concerns in ChatGPT such as GDPR compliance, data transparency, etc.</i>	13
Regulation	<i>Need for AI regulation to protect rights and prevent misuse</i>	10
Limiting opportunities	<i>Banning ChatGPT limits opportunities for residents in Italy</i>	9
Fear	<i>Banning ChatGPT because they were afraid of it</i>	7
Useful tool	<i>ChatGPT can assist and help in various tasks</i>	6
Embrace	<i>ChatGPT is a part of our lives and we should accept it</i>	4
Education	<i>Need to educate people of such technologies</i>	3
Other	<i>[falls outside of the established themes]</i>	1

Students’ perceptions. After completing the NLP unit, students acknowledged that technologies such as smart assistants require a huge volume of data for training. They highlighted the need to train models with high-quality datasets to have good results. Some students were also able to understand privacy and ethical considerations surrounding NLP and AI systems, in general. This finding aligns with Dobesh et al.’s work [7], which demonstrated that after attending an NLP course aimed to raise awareness of fairness in ML systems, students were able to identify how biases can be introduced and amplified by NLP systems. Similar to previous work [12, 13] we found that attending training on AI technologies, boosts learners’ awareness of how these technologies work, understand associated ethical issues and critically evaluate them.

As expected, most students had used ChatGPT before the course, either to generate text and essays or even code. Similar to previous work [35] students found it efficient, and they were impressed by its capabilities. When asked about their thoughts on banning ChatGPT, there was little consistency across opinions. It was not a surprise that the majority mentioned privacy concerns and the need for regulation. Some participants mentioned that banning ChatGPT led to limiting the opportunities of Italian residents. It was reassuring that a few students reported the view that ChatGPT and relevant technologies will be a part of our lives, and thus, we need to embrace their potential and become more educated about them. This was consistent with [37], which suggested that while banning is not the solution, the public needs to be aware of these technologies and their ethical considerations. Our findings align with prior work [27] which indicated that students are using ChatGPT, but there is a need for specific guidelines and classroom assessments.

Insights for the educational intervention. The unit successfully engaged students in understanding NLP. We observed that integrating hands-on assignments which did not require coding, like creating a smart assistant, played a crucial role in understanding the challenges of developing NLP systems. Since most of our students lacked a CS background or programming experience, they felt empowered using a tool that allowed them to create an NLP system. This method not only opened up access to AI development for students without coding skills but also provided students with a tangible understanding of the challenges inherent when developing such systems which was one of the main aims of the unit.

Another valuable lesson from this unit was the importance of including discussion topics that are timely and popular. Contextualizing course content within current issues, such as the ChatGPT ban in Italy, sparked dynamic discussions among our students. This

timely event caught their attention and elicited more thoughtful and extensive responses in the assignments. We recommend future educators adopt a similar approach, integrating examples and discussions that align with students’ experiences.

Limitations. There are some limitations that should be considered when interpreting these results. Our students were a small number (N=25) of young, primarily undergraduates, studying at the same university, and most were from the same country (Italy). Lastly, students registered for this course probably because they were interested in AI; hence, their responses should not be generalized. Future work is needed with larger and more diverse audiences, to fully understand if a short educational intervention can impact the understanding of students about topics such as NLP and LLMs.

7 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The increasing influence of NLP applications in everyday life, and in particular, the interactivity and “human-likeness” of generative AI applications such as those driven by LLMs, has resulted in an urgent need to educate the public. Users need to understand these technologies, both in terms of their capabilities, and their limitations. In this paper, we present our experience teaching a unit of NLP as a part of an AI course to non-CS students. Using the responses of our students to the unit’s assignment, we provide insights into their understanding of NLP and surrounding the decision to ban ChatGPT in Italy. Overall, our experience teaching NLP to non-CS students indicates that students can understand and appreciate topics like AI and NLP. The integration of hands-on activities and discussion on current topics enriches the educational experience comprehensively. As AI keeps advancing, educators should use lively and relevant teaching methods, helping students learn both the technical and the ethical and social aspects of AI.

To further understand perceptions of NLP and ChatGPT in education, future research should expand sample sizes with students from different universities to capture diverse perspectives. Additionally, examining both the short-term and long-term effects of education interventions about NLP will help understand its impact on students’ learning outcomes. Finally, investigating how NLP systems such as ChatGPT can be used in educational settings will help determine the most effective ways to utilize such tools.

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